

Thrombolysis: Are the results from the clinical trial meta-analysis seen in real life outcomes? A machine learning study of the UK stroke registry.

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Abstract

Introduction: This study examines the effect of thrombolysis on discharge outcomes for ischaemic stroke patients in England and Wales using data from the UK prospective national stroke registry.

Patients and methods: A total of 168,347 ischaemic stroke patients who attended one of 118 emergency stroke hospitals in England and Wales from 2016 to 2021 were extracted from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP). We used explainable machine learning (XGBoost with SHAP) to examine the effect of patient characteristics, hospital attended, and use/time of thrombolysis on the odds of achieving a good outcome (being at or below any given modified Rankin Scale threshold). A linear regression model was fitted to the estimated effect of onset-to-treatment time on thrombolysis to permit comparison with clinical trial meta-analyses.

Results: Thrombolysis was found to be associated with a statistically significant improvement in the odds of having a good outcome using any mRS threshold. Regression analysis predicted a maximum 2.5-fold improvement in odds of achieving mRS 0-1, with a decline to no treatment effect at 5 hours 28 minutes post-onset.

Discussion and Conclusion: Our results confirm a beneficial effect of thrombolysis in a large prospective national stroke registry, and align closely with meta-analyses of clinical trials of thrombolysis both in terms of magnitude of effect and decline over time. This work also demonstrates the potential of applying explainable machine learning to observational data to extend understanding of stroke treatment outcomes for patient cohorts not included in the original clinical trials.

Plain English Summary

What is the problem? Use of clot-busting treatment (*'thrombolysis'*) in stroke varies a great deal between hospitals.

What did we know? We knew that the largest cause of this variation was from how willing doctors are to use thrombolysis. Some doctors are worried that use of this treatment in the real world won't have the same benefit that was predicted by the clinical trials.

What did we not know? We did not know what the effect of thrombolysis is in the real world across

all types of patients where thrombolysis has been used.

What did we do? We used explainable machine learning to learn how much patients benefit from thrombolysis in real world use. Machine learning finds patterns in large sets of data and can predict outcomes of patients. *Explainable* machine learning allows us to see what affects outcomes. We were particularly interested here in how use of thrombolysis affects outcomes.

What did we find out? We found out that thrombolysis was at least as effective in real world use as clinical trials predicted.

1 Introduction

Stroke remains one of the top three global causes of death and disability¹. Despite reductions in age-standardised rates of stroke, ageing populations are driving an increase in the absolute number of strokes¹. Across Europe, in 2017, stroke was estimated to cost healthcare systems €27 billion, or 1.7% of health expenditure². The burden is increasing; it has been estimated that the number of stroke survivors aged 45 and over in the UK will more than double between 2015 and 2035³.

Thrombolysis with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator, can significantly reduce disability after ischaemic stroke, provided it is given in the first few hours after stroke onset⁴.

Despite thrombolysis being of proven benefit in ischaemic stroke, use of thrombolysis varies significantly both between and within European countries⁵. In England and Wales the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP) reported that in 2021/22, 20 years after the original European Medicines Agency licencing of alteplase for acute ischaemic stroke, thrombolysis rates varied from 1% to 28% of emergency stroke admissions between hospitals⁶, with a median rate of 10.4% and an inter-quartile range of 8%-13%, against a 2019 NHS England long term plan that 20% of patients with stroke should be receiving thrombolysis⁷.

Studies have shown that reasons for low and varying thrombolysis rates are multi-factorial. Reasons include late presentation⁵, lack of expertise⁵ or lack of clear protocols or training⁸, delayed access to specialists⁹, and poor triage by ambulance or emergency department staff⁸. For many factors, the establishment of primary stroke centres has been suggested to improve the emergency care of patients with stroke and reduce barriers to thrombolysis⁸, with a centralised model of primary stroke centres leading to increased likelihood of thrombolysis^{10;11;12}.

In addition to organisational factors, clinicians can have varying attitudes to which patients are suitable candidates for thrombolysis. In a discrete choice experiment¹³, 138 clinicians considered hypothetical patient vignettes, and responded as to whether they would give the patients thrombolysis. The authors concluded that there was considerable heterogeneity among respondents in their thrombolysis decision-making. Areas of difference were around whether to give thrombolysis to mild strokes, to older patients beyond 3 hours from stroke onset, and when there was pre-existing disability. We have also found, from interviews, that some clinicians express a lack of faith in the clinical trials of thrombolysis and demonstrated a reluctance to expressed a lack of faith in the clinical trials and reluctance to thrombolysed due to perceived risks of the procedure¹⁴.

Based on national audit data from three years of emergency stroke admissions, we have previously built models of the emergency stroke pathway using clinical pathway simulation to examine the potential scale of the effect of changing two aspects of the stroke pathway performance (1. the in-hospital process speeds, and 2. the proportion of patients with a determined stroke onset time), and using machine learning to examine the effect of replicating clinical decision-making around thrombolysis from higher thrombolysing hospitals to lower thrombolysing hospitals^{15;16}. We showed that it would be credible to target an increase

in average thrombolysis in England and Wales, from 11% to 18%, but that each hospital should have its own target, reflecting differences in local populations. We found that the largest increase in thrombolysis use would come from replicating thrombolysis decision-making practice from higher to lower thrombolysing hospitals.

In order to further understand the variation around thrombolysis decision-making, we employed explainable machine learning to understand how patient characteristics and the hospital attended affect the odds of a patient receiving thrombolysis¹⁷. We found that the odds of receiving thrombolysis varied 13 fold between hospitals, with lower thrombolysing hospitals especially more likely to avoid thrombolysis in non-ideal candidates such as patients with mild stroke, or with pre-stroke disability.

Qualitative research has identified that clinicians from stroke teams with low thrombolysis use are concerned about the risk:benefit profile of thrombolysis¹⁴. Confidence in the benefit of thrombolysis was especially lower in Emergency Department clinicians (as opposed to specialist stroke consultants), and there was more concern around patients that were seen as marginal candidates for thrombolysis, such as mild stroke.

There have been various observational studies which have provided further support for the effectiveness of thrombolysis^{18;19;20;21}. None of these studies, however, were able to investigate the relationship between time-to-treatment and effectiveness compared to the clinical trial meta-analyses.

With the collection of clinical data for all emergency stroke admissions in England and Wales, and with the power of new explainable machine learning techniques, our aim was to build a predictive model of stroke outcomes, perform a large scale analysis of the benefit of thrombolysis in practice, and to compare the relationship between time-to-treatment and effectiveness with clinical trial results.

2 Method

2.1 Data

Data were retrieved for 168,347 emergency ischaemic stroke admissions to hospitals in England and Wales for six calendar years, 2016–2021 (inclusive), obtained from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP). SSNAP prospectively collects clinical data from 100% of acute hospitals in England and Wales, with case ascertainment estimated at >90% when compared with administrative coding data. Data fields were provided for the hyperacute phase of the stroke pathway, up to and including the primary outcome of disability at inpatient discharge, recorded using the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) score. The data includes 118 acute stroke hospitals (each with at least 250 stroke admissions and which delivered thrombolysis to at least 10 patients in the study period), for patients that arrived at the hospital by ambulance after their stroke onset and did not go on to receive thrombectomy (rates of thrombectomy recorded in SSNAP increased from 0.7% to 2.0% of all stroke during this period).

2.2 Feature selection

The full dataset contained 57 features that described patient demographic and clinical characteristics, the acute stroke pathway, use/time of thrombolysis, and the stroke team they attended). We applied the feature selection results from Pearn *et al.*²², which used modelling and discussions with clinicians to identify the influential features to include in the model.

Code and full results for feature selection may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/feature_selection_thrombolysis_outcome_ml_paper

2.3 Machine learning models

We trained a set of six independent XGBoost models²³ to predict the likelihood of an ischaemic stroke patient attaining any given mRS threshold at discharge. For each mRS threshold, we refer to being at or lower than that threshold as a '*same or better*' or '*good outcome*'. We used 5-fold cross validation to test the accuracy of the model, and to test reproducibility of patterns detected (in 5-fold cross validation the data is split into 5 different 80:20 train/test splits with each patient being in one, and only one, test set). The results from the model fitted on the first k-fold split was used to investigate the relationships between feature values and their contribution to the predictions.

Code, and full results, for the machine learning work may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/thrombolysis_clinical_trials_ml_paper

2.4 Model accuracy

For each of the six machine learning models, we report the model accuracy measured using the 5-fold model: percent correct and receiver operating characteristic area under curve (ROC-AUC).

2.5 SHapley Additive exPlanation (SHAP) values

SHAP values explain the contribution (as the change in log-odds) that each feature value has on the model's prediction of achieving a good outcome at discharge²⁴. SHAP values expressed as log-odds are additive (and so are preferred to probabilities, which are not additive, when examining the contribution of individual features to the final prediction). A SHAP model for each of the six machine learning models was created (one for each threshold of mRS). To illustrate how to interpret the SHAP value in our case, the target feature with a value of 1 represents a good outcome (being at or below any given mRS threshold), and a value 0 represents a worse outcome (being above any given mRS threshold). A positive SHAP value represents that the corresponding feature value increases the likelihood for that patient having a good outcome, and a negative SHAP value represents that the corresponding feature value reduces the likelihood for that patient having a good outcome. SHAP values can be assessed *locally* at patient level, and *globally* at patient cohort level to understand general patterns of how discharge outcomes differ by each of the patient, pathway, and hospital characteristics.

2.6 Counterfactual treatment (what if patients had not received thrombolysis?)

We used counterfactuals for each patient who received thrombolysis, to assess the contribution that thrombolysis made on the likelihood of a good outcome at discharge. Limiting this analysis to the 6,897 patients that receive thrombolysis in the first k-fold test set, we created their counterfactual case by setting the feature *onset to treatment time* to 9,999 minutes (the same value used to train the model, for patients who did not receive thrombolysis) to represent the patient not receiving treatment, and used the model to predict their counterfactual outcome.

2.6.1 The direct contribution of thrombolysis use to the shift in probability of a good outcome

Taking the difference between the predicted log odds for a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge, contributed by the *onset to thrombolysis time* feature, when the patient received thrombolysis, and not, gave the predicted shift in likelihood of a good outcome at discharge with thrombolysis for each patient who received thrombolysis. We modelled the decay in effect of thrombolysis by fitting a linear regression model to the benefit of thrombolysis (log odds shift in attaining a good outcome) with time from onset to

treatment (excluding patients treated after 300 minutes). The model used the definition of mRS 0-1 as a good outcome to match the definition used in the meta analysis of clinical trials⁴. The analysis was applied to three patient cohorts: (1) all ischaemic strokes (n = 6,897), (2) severe ischaemic strokes, NIHSS 11+ (n = 2,897), (3) mild-moderate ischaemic strokes, NIHSS 0-10 (n = 4,000).

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive statistics

The 168,347 patients (who had onset-to-scan of within 255 minutes) attended 118 hospitals with admissions ranging from 358 to 4,559, with thrombolysis rates ranging from 5.9% to 39.2%. Of those 133,516 patients that did not receive thrombolysis, their range of disability at discharge was: 12% mRS 0, 33% mRS 0-1, 52% mRS 0-2, 69% mRS 0-3, 82% mRS 0-4, and 88% mRS 0-5 at discharge. Of those 34,831 patients that received thrombolysis, their range of disability at discharge was: 15% mRS 0, 35% mRS 0-1, 54% mRS 0-2, 69% mRS 0-3, 81% mRS 0-4, and 86% mRS 0-5.

Table 1 shows further descriptive statistics for the patients who received thrombolysis.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for patients who received thrombolysis

Patient feature	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Q1	Q2	Q3	Max
Age (5 year age bands)	73	13	37.5	62.5	72.5	82.5	92.5
Proportion male	0.55	-	-	-	-	-	-
Prior disability (mRS)	0.8	1.2	0	0	0	1	5
Stroke severity (NIHSS)	10.8	7.0	0	5	9	16	42
Onset to thrombolysis time (minutes)	163	60	7	120	155	198	720
Discharge disability (mRS)	2.6	1.9	0	1	2	4	6

3.2 Feature selection

Using the results from Pearn *et al.*²², we selected 7 features as inputs for the model to predict a patient’s likelihood of a good outcome at discharge:

1. Prior disability level: Disability level (mRS) before stroke
2. Stroke severity: Stroke severity (NIHSS) on arrival
3. Stroke team: Attended hospital
4. Age: Age (as middle of 5 year age bands)
5. Onset to thrombolysis time: Time from onset to receiving thrombolysis (minutes). This was set to 9,999 if the patient did not receive thrombolysis.
6. Atrial fibrillation diagnosis: Patient had a diagnosis of atrial fibrillation (either on arrival or diagnosed during admission)
7. Precise onset known: Onset time recorded was recorded as being precise time (as opposed to a best estimate)

3.3 Model accuracy

With 7 input features, overall accuracy ranged from 77.6% to 89.7% across the six models (standard deviation across the 5 k-folds ranged from 0.001 to 0.002). This represented between 95-98% of the accuracy that is obtained with all the features as inputs. ROC-AUC ranged from 0.852 to 0.893 across the six models (standard deviation across the 5 k-folds ranged from 0.001 to 0.002). Results were reproducible across the 5 k-folds, so further analysis was performed on the first k-fold split.

3.4 Individual patient SHAP values

SHAP values were calculated for each feature for each instance as how each value affects the log odds of having a good outcome at discharge. Figure 1 shows a waterfall plot that illustrates the contribution from each feature value on the prediction for whether this individual patient had a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge. This example patient (received thrombolysis at 165 minutes, known precisely, with no prior disability, 72.5 years old, had a moderate stroke, and attended hospital number 103) has a predicted 0.479 log odds (equivalent to 62% probability) of having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge. For this patient, the two most influential features (that both increased the likelihood of having a good outcome, mRS 0-1) were prior disability (mRS 0) and onset to thrombolysis time (165 minutes).

Figure 1: The waterfall plot for a single patient showing the influence of the nine most influential feature values (y-axis) on the predicted likelihood of having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) on discharge (x-axis). Features are ranked in order of importance (top being most influential), with the contribution from the 10th ranked feature onwards being represented as a single contribution (*115 other features*). The features with name prefix *"team_"* refers to a stroke team, where the value 1 represents the attended team, and the value 0 represents a team not attended (which may also have a small effect in the model). Each machine learning model applies the same SHAP base value ($E[f(X)]$) to each patient, this can be interpreted as the most likely outcome given no other knowledge of the instance. The sum of the SHAP base value and the SHAP values for each input feature equates to the overall predicted likelihood of having a good outcome on discharge, shown at the top of the plot ($f(x)$).

3.5 Global SHAP patterns

For each patient in the test set we extracted SHAP values for each feature with its corresponding feature value. Figure 2a shows the relationship between feature values and the odds of a patient having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge (a positive SHAP value contributes to an increased likelihood, and a negative SHAP value contributes to a reduced likelihood). We see that low prior disability, lower stroke severity, younger age, receiving thrombolysis (and receiving it sooner after onset), and having no diagnosis of atrial fibrillation contributed to a patient more likely having a good outcome at discharge. Figure 2b focusses on the feature *onset to thrombolysis time*, and its effect at reaching any disability threshold. As time from onset to treatment increased, the beneficial effect of thrombolysis decayed. For thresholds up to, and including, mRS 3, the median effect of thrombolysis remained positive, compared to not receiving thrombolysis, up until the maximum time of 720 minutes. For thresholds of mRS 4 and upwards, the median effect of thrombolysis became negative at longer onset-to-treatment times. This was especially apparent in how thrombolysis changed the overall odds of survival (mRS 0-5) where the median effect of thrombolysis became negative from about 155 minutes. Later thrombolysis may therefore increase the proportion of patients attaining mRS 0-3, but at the cost of some reduction in overall survival. Earlier thrombolysis improved the odds of survival. Figure 2c shows the contribution from attending a specific hospital to predicting whether the patient had a good outcome at discharge, for each of the mRS threshold levels used to define a good outcome. As the threshold for having a good outcome becomes more inclusive, the range of the effect of the hospital attended had a reduced contribution on the prediction.

3.6 Counterfactuals (what if patients had not received thrombolysis?)

3.6.1 For an individual patient

Figure 3 shows the waterfall plot for a single patient who received thrombolysis (figure 3a), and its counterfactual case had the same patient not received thrombolysis (figure 3b). This patient had a predicted 0.479 log odds (62% probability) of having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge with thrombolysis, and -0.671 (34% probability) without thrombolysis. By comparing the log odds contributed by the feature *onset to thrombolysis time* in both cases (when the patient received thrombolysis, and not), we can isolate the predicted direct contribution to a good outcome of being given thrombolysis at a specified duration from stroke onset. For the patient in figure 3 the predicted direct contribution to a good outcome (mRS 0-1) for being given thrombolysis at 165 minutes from stroke onset was 0.69 log odds (feature *onset to thrombolysis time* contributed 0.57 log odds to the likelihood of a good outcome when given at 165 minutes, and -0.12 log odds when not given).

3.6.2 For a cohort of patients

Using the counterfactual results for all of the patients in the first k-fold test set that received thrombolysis ($n = 6,897$), figure 4 shows the shift in predicted probability of a good outcome at discharge, had they not received thrombolysis. For the majority of the cases, there is a greater probability for a good outcome with thrombolysis.

3.6.3 The direct contribution of thrombolysis use to the shift in probability of a good outcome

Using the counterfactual results for all of the patients in the first k-fold test set that received thrombolysis within 300 minutes from stroke onset ($n = 6,796$), figure 5 shows a linear regression fitted to the shift in the contribution from receiving thrombolysis towards having a good outcome at discharge (mRS 0-1) with respect to the onset to thrombolysis time. We found, for all treated patients, that the effect of thrombolysis had declined to zero at 328 minutes, and the effect from thrombolysis was improving log

odds of a good outcome by 0.90 if it were, theoretically, given at the time of stroke onset. We observed that the maximum theoretical effect of thrombolysis (if given at time of stroke onset) was greater for the severe stroke group (1.048 log odds) than the mild-moderate stroke group (0.771 log odds). However the effect of thrombolysis declined a little faster in the severe stroke group (reaching no effect at 314 minutes for severe stroke patients, compared to 351 minutes for mild-moderate stroke patients). Linear regression coefficients in all three patient groups were statistically significant (table 2).

Table 2: Fitting linear regression to the shift in the contribution from receiving thrombolysis towards having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge with respect to the onset to thrombolysis (OTT) time. Linear regression statistics for different patient cohorts. We used NIHSS 0-10 to define mild-moderate strokes, and NIHSS 11+ to define severe strokes.

Ischaemic stroke type	Variables	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
All	Constant	0.9012	0.007	132.519	0.000	0.888	0.915
	OTT time (min)	-0.0027	4.04e-05	-68.058	0.000	-0.003	-0.003
Severe	Constant	1.0476	0.011	96.746	0.000	1.026	1.069
	OTT time (mins)	-0.0033	6.67e-05	-50.042	0.000	-0.003	-0.003
Mild-moderate	Constant	0.7708	0.008	97.613	0.000	0.755	0.786
	OTT (mins)	-0.0022	4.57e-05	-48.109	0.000	-0.002	-0.002

(a) The relationship between feature values and the prediction of whether a patient will have a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge. SHAP base value for this model is -1.529.

(b) The relationship between onset to thrombolysis time and the prediction of whether a patient will have a good outcome at discharge, for each of the mRS scores used to define a good outcome.

(c) The contribution from attending a specific hospital to predicting whether the patient will have a good outcome at discharge, for each of the mRS scores used to define a good outcome

Figure 2: The relationship between feature values and SHAP values in predicting whether a patient will have a good outcome. Violin plots show the distribution of SHAP values across the patient population for each feature value, with the mid-line showing the median SHAP value.

(a) Patient with original data (received thrombolysis at 165 minutes)

(b) Counterfactual case of the same patient not receiving thrombolysis (set onset-to-thrombolysis time to 9999 minutes)

Figure 3: The waterfall plot for a single patient, and its counterfactual case, showing the influence of the nine most influential feature values (y-axis) on the predicted likelihood of having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) on discharge (x-axis). Features are ranked in order of importance (top being most influential), with the contribution from the 10th ranked feature onwards being represented as a single contribution (*115 other features*). The features with name prefix "team_" refers to a stroke team, where the value 1 represents the attended team, and the value 0 represents a team not attended. Each machine learning model applies the same SHAP base value ($E[f(X)]$) to each patient, this can be interpreted as the most likely outcome given no other knowledge of the instance. The sum of the SHAP base value and the SHAP values for each input feature equates to the overall predicted likelihood of having a good outcome on discharge, shown at the top of the plot ($f(x)$).

Figure 4: The predicted probability of attaining a good outcome with and without thrombolysis, for those patients in the test population that received thrombolysis. Each plot shows the different mRS thresholds used to define a good outcome. The solid black line denotes no change ($x=y$). The white square shows the same patient across all six plots.

Figure 5: A linear regression fit to the contribution from receiving thrombolysis on having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge, with respect to the onset to thrombolysis time (for patients treated within 300 minutes). Top: all treated stroke patients ($n = 6,796$); Middle: treated severe stroke patients, NIHSS 11+ ($n = 2,856$); Bottom: treated mild-moderate stroke patients, NIHSS 0-10 ($n = 3,940$).

4 Discussion

We built explainable machine learning models based on comprehensive prospective national stroke registry data capable of predicting disability outcome, at any given disability threshold, with high performance. The most influential factors that favoured being at or below any given disability threshold were lower pre-stroke disability, lower stroke severity, younger age, and use and speed of thrombolysis. The stroke team attended also had an effect on achieving any disability threshold, and that effect reduced with increasing disability at discharge. This could be due to 1) some hospitals discharging patients earlier with more disability e.g. with more community rehabilitation available, 2) effects of other hospital treatments on outcomes e.g. better/worse stroke unit care, or 3) hospitals assessing disability at discharge differently. From our model we cannot speculate further, but by including stroke team in the model we can adjust the model for these effects, allowing a clearer view of other patient features affecting outcome.

The model allows for counterfactual analysis, predicting outcomes with or without thrombolysis for any patient. In this analysis we focussed on predicting outcomes without thrombolysis, for those that actually received thrombolysis. In this way we investigate the effect of thrombolysis in those that did actually receive it. Using SHAP values, which explain the contribution of feature values to model prediction, we can also isolate the effect of thrombolysis. We found thrombolysis improved the odds of being at or below any given disability threshold, but the effect of thrombolysis was lower, and decayed to no-effect sooner, for outcomes of mRS ≤ 5 and ≤ 6 . We found that the effect of thrombolysis was present for both mild-moderate and severe strokes, but with a larger effect in severe strokes. The findings from this study were remarkably similar to the meta-analysis of clinical trials⁴, which extrapolate back to a 0.69 log odds (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.0) improvement of being mRS 0-1 at stroke onset, with no effect after 378 minutes (6.3 hours). Our maximum theoretical improvement in log odds of achieving mRS 0-1 was a little higher at 0.90 (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.5), with a decline to no-effect at 328 minutes (5.5 hours), indicating a somewhat steeper decline in effectiveness with time in our observational real-world study when compared to the original randomised data. This is likely to be due to the licencing conditions for alteplase, in that the meta-analysis included randomised trials out to 6 hours from stroke onset⁴, whereas the overwhelming majority of patients treated in the UK over the six-year study period were restricted to guideline-based eligibility within 4.5 hours²⁵.

The findings from this study were similar to the meta-analyses of clinical trials⁴, which extrapolate back to a 0.69 log odds (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.0) improvement of being mRS 0-1 at stroke onset, with no effect after 378 minutes (6.3 hours). Our maximum theoretical improvement in log odds improvement of being mRS 0-1 was a little higher, at 0.90 (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.5), with a decline to no-effect at 328 minutes (5.5 hours).

Because of the size of the data available in the nationwide registry SSNAP, we are able to build more complex models than those derived from clinical trials, investigating stroke outcomes and benefit/disbenefit across a range of patient subgroups extending beyond the strict eligibility of randomised trials, and including comparisons of decision-making and outcomes between stroke teams. This has, for example, allowed us to address the additional effect on outcomes from lower-thrombolysing teams adopting the less conservative practices in the use of thrombolysis found in higher thrombolysing teams. Companion papers to this paper explore these questions further^{22;26}. We have shown elsewhere that the majority of variation in thrombolysis rates between hospitals in the UK is accounted for by differences in clinical decision making, particularly around ‘less than ideal’ candidates for thrombolysis^{16;15;26}. The data in the current study show that in such patients there is a systematic disposition towards benefit at any level of disability outcome that supports the greater use of thrombolysis among patients not typically eligible for the original randomised trials.

The clinical significance of this work is that we have confirmed the net benefit of thrombolysis in a very

large prospective national stroke registry that encompasses patients outside the strictly defined eligibility of the original randomised trials, and used sophisticated machine learning with SHAP to isolate the effect of thrombolysis from other patient characteristics that influence outcomes. This provides significant reassurance that in real-world clinical practice, the anticipated benefits of thrombolysis are being delivered, even when treatment is deployed in a wider spectrum of patients than those represented in the randomised trials.

In summary, applying explainable machine learning to an observational data set demonstrated that the effectiveness of thrombolysis in the *real world* appears to be at least as good as the clinical trials indicated. Our results should give stroke clinicians more confidence that the beneficial effect of thrombolysis is seen in real treatment populations. The size of the observational data set allows for more detailed analysis of the benefit of thrombolysis in subgroups of patients.

4.1 Study limitations

Though we are using a very large data set, our study necessarily has some limitations:

- A group of more severely affected stroke patients who proceeded to receive thrombectomy has been excluded from the analysis, although during the six year study period endovascular intervention was increasing from a low base in the UK, and increased from 0.7% to 2.0% of all stroke.
- There is always a risk of inherent biases of an observational sample. Though our model has good accuracy, it remains possible that there are confounding patient characteristics that have an influence on the decision to treat, or the patient outcome, that are not measured in SSNAP.
- We have used the mRS at hospital discharge as our primary outcome, whereas the trials used the mRS at 90 days. We know that the two are highly correlated²⁷, though individual patients may get better or worse between discharge and 90 days (possibly reflecting other aspects of care, such as community rehabilitation programmes).

4.2 Further work

Considering recent suggestions that thrombolysis should not be used in mild stroke^{28:29}, a more in-depth study of the observed effect of thrombolysis mild stroke, combining machine learning with causal inference methods such as propensity-score adjustment³⁰ or target trial emulation³¹, would add to the evidence base around in this contentious group of patients.

5 References

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Informed consent and Ethics

As we are using anonymised secondary data, collected for national audit, individual consent is not required. SSNAP has approval under section 251 of the NHS Health and Social Care Act (2006) to collect patient level data on the first six months of patient care (ECC 6- 02(FT3)/2012), without requiring individual patient consent. Access to SSNAP data is managed by the UK Healthcare Quality Improvement Partnership (HQIP), with this project being approved by HQIP (HQIP303). More information on SSNAPs use of patient data may be found at: <https://www.strokeaudit.org/SupportFiles/Documents/Patient-area-documents/Fair-processingstatement-for-patients-v7-0.aspx>

As we are using anonymised secondary data, collected for national audit, used for service evaluation and improvement, no ethical approval is required (confirmed using the NHS Health Research Authority decision aid: <https://www.hra-decisiontools.org.uk/ethics/>).

Guarantor

The corresponding author, Michael Allen, is the guarantor of the paper (PI on the NIHR project funding).